

Artificial Pancreas: challenges for safe and efficient glucose control*

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Abstract

Despite the technological advances of the last years, glucose control in type 1 diabetes still remains a challenging task. The main features that complicate the control problems are the high inter- and intra-patient variability and the limitations in data collection due to safety concerns. This work presents the last achievements related to the development of an artificial pancreas able to adapt itself to the system changes over the time. Inter-patient variability is addressed through personalized models, exploring classical impulse-response technique and hybrid physics-informed neural networks. Soft-switched multi-model MPCs and periodic MPCs have been developed to manage intra-patient variability. Safety is enhanced via asymmetric cost functions based on the clinical index and predictive layers have been designed for early hypoglycemia detection/prevention and meal estimation. Simulations with the UVA/Padova T1D simulator show better glucose control in terms of time in target range and hypoglycemia reduction.

Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) is a widespread autoimmune disease that affects millions of people worldwide [1]. The absence of insulin production in patients with T1D results in prolonged periods of hyperglycemia (Blood Glucose (BG) > 180 mg/dl), which can have harmful long-term effects. External insulin injections allow patients with T1D to manage elevated BG levels. However, the dosage has to be carefully computed to avoid the dangerous condition of hypoglycemia (BG < 70 mg/dl).

The primary goal for T1D individuals is to prevent both hypo- and hyperglycemia, maintaining the BG levels inside the safe range of [70-180] mg/dl. The Artificial Pancreas (AP) systems tackles this challenge through a closed-loop architecture that includes a subcutaneous (sc) glucose sensor, a sc insulin pump, and a control algorithm. The goal of the AP is to compute an optimal insulin therapy via the control algorithm to compensate meals and other disturbances and to adapt the therapy to the patient changes. This is a challenging goal since the sc-to-sc glucose-insulin system is characterized by significant delays, in addition to inter- and intra-patient variability. Moreover, safety constraints are crucial to prevent dangerous events such as

hypoglycemia and they have to be included in the design of the AP. One of the most promising approaches explored in the last decades is the Model Predictive Control (MPC) [2] which allows to compute the control action considering the constraints.

Inter-patient variability

Glucose control has to account for the substantial variability in glucose-insulin dynamics between patients due to differences in metabolic parameters, insulin sensitivity and daily habits. It calls for patient-tailored control strategies, so predictive models used in MPC have to be identified for each subject. Two modeling approaches have been considered: the first relies on classical identification techniques, with a linear Impulse-Response (IR) model [3] built from simulated data using the UVA/Padova T1D simulator and then customized to a specific patient via a constrained optimization on real data. This approach provides interpretable and control-oriented models, since impulse-like responses to insulin or meals are available. The second approach exploits advanced machine learning techniques such as Large Language Models (LLMs) or Long Short-term Memory networks (LSTMs) that can capture non-linear dynamics. However, pure data-driven models often struggle to disentangle the effects of overlapping inputs (e.g., insulin and meals occurring contemporarily), which limits their reliability in control applications. To overcome these limitations, a hybrid physics-informed LSTM architecture is proposed in [4], embedding the mechanistic IR model as a backbone and learning a nonlinear residual via LSTM. This preserves interpretability while enhancing flexibility improving the prediction of individual input effects by over 200% and reducing prediction errors by up

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to 40% in challenging scenarios. Another well established method to account for inter-patient variability consists in a run-to-run adjustment of the output-tracking weight in the MPC cost function for each patient, adapting the aggressiveness of the response to the single patient [5].

Intra-patient variability

The glucose control problem is complicated by the presence of a well-known circadian pattern in insulin sensitivity. A multiple-model approach is proposed in [6] to take it into account: three glucose-insulin models (breakfast, lunch and dinner) are identified and embedded in a multi-MPC scheme. Rather than using abrupt switching between models [7], a soft-switching mechanism is implemented to ensure physiologically plausible and smooth transitions across different periods. Specifically, all three controllers are simultaneously active, but their influence is modulated over time through dynamic weights. Near meal transition times, two controllers are blended linearly, while the third remains inactive. This interpolation process is controlled by a parameter that enables fine-tuning of overlap and smoothness. Considering the limited computational resources, the three models can be merged into a single periodic framework [8]. Specifically, a periodic multiple model predictor paired with a periodic Kalman filter and a periodic MPC is designed to capture circadian insulin sensitivity variations. In silico tests on a case-study subject showed that this compact approach nearly doubled the 1-hour prediction FIT (from 39.7% to 81.9%) and fully eliminated the postprandial hypoglycemic events over a 30-day free-living scenario, while reducing computational burden compared to the multi-MPC scheme.

Safety layer

APs have to guarantee patient safety different approaches have been studied. Instead of relying on threshold-based alerts, a LSTM-based system is proposed in [9] to trigger an alarm when a risk of hypoglycemia is detected, allowing prompt corrective actions. Additionally, safety can be further enhanced through the adoption of a MPC with an asymmetric stage cost [10] to penalize deviations toward hypoglycemia more heavily than those toward hyperglycemia, reflecting the higher short-term risk of low BG. The asymmetry is achieved by incorporating the Blood Glucose Index (BGI) (Figure 1) in the cost function to prioritize the avoidance of hypoglycemia. The stability of this asymmetric MPC formulation, particularly in relation to terminal ingredients, is currently under investigation. To further improve fault tolerance, data-driven residual generators based on parity-space techniques have been studied [12], enabling detection and isolation of unannounced disturbances such as untreated meals. Upon detecting such a meal-related fault and estimating the associated carbohydrate intake, the system can operate in fully closed-loop mode, autonomously delivering the corrective bolus without requiring user input, thus reducing the burden on the patient.

Figure 1: Blood Glucose Index (blue solid line) [11]. Glucose target \bar{y} represented by the orange dashed line.

References

- [1] H. Sun, P. Saeedi, S. Karuranga, M. Pinkepank, K. Ogurtsova, B. B. Duncan, C. Stein, A. Basit, J. C. Chan, J. C. Mbanya *et al.*, “IDF Diabetes Atlas: Global, regional and country-level diabetes prevalence estimates for 2021 and projections for 2045,” *Diabetes research and clinical practice*, vol. 183, p. 109119, 2022.
- [2] J. Kropff, S. Del Favero, J. Place, C. Toffanin, R. Visentin, M. Monaro, M. Messori, F. Di Palma, G. Lanzola, A. Farret *et al.*, “2 month evening and night closed-loop glucose control in patients with type 1 diabetes under free-living conditions: a randomised crossover trial,” *The lancet Diabetes & endocrinology*, vol. 3, no. 12, pp. 939–947, 2015.
- [3] C. Toffanin and L. Magni, “Personalized Constrained MPC for glucose regulation,” in *22nd World Congress of the International Federation of Automatic Control (IFAC)*, 2023.
- [4] P. A. Mongini, M. Drecogna, and C. Toffanin, “New physics-LSTM hybrid models for control-oriented glucose prediction in type 1 diabetes,” in *2025 American control conference (ACC)*, 2025, Accepted.
- [5] C. Toffanin, R. Visentin, M. Messori, F. Di Palma, L. Magni, and C. Cobelli, “Toward a run-to-run adaptive artificial pancreas: In silico results,” *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 65, no. 3, pp. 479–488, 2017.
- [6] M. Ragni, P. A. Mongini, L. Magni, and C. Toffanin, “Multiple constrained MPCs for glucose regulation in type 1 diabetes,” in *1st IFAC Workshop on Engineering Diabetes Technology*, 2025, Accepted.
- [7] C. Toffanin, E. Aiello, S. Del Favero, C. Cobelli, and L. Magni, “Multiple models for artificial pancreas predictions identified from free-living condition data: A proof of concept study,” *Journal of Process Control*, vol. 77, pp. 29–37, 2019.
- [8] P. A. Mongini, M. Ragni, L. Magni, and C. Toffanin, “Periodic MPC for glucose control in type 1 diabetes,” in *1st IFAC Workshop on Engineering Diabetes Technology*, 2025, Accepted.
- [9] M. Drecogna, C. Cobelli, and C. Toffanin, “Personalized lstm-based alarm systems for hypoglycemia prevention in an intraperitoneal artificial pancreas,” in *2024 32nd Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 233–238.
- [10] M. Messori, M. Ellis, C. Cobelli, P. D. Christofides, and L. Magni, “Improved postprandial glucose control with a customized model predictive controller,” in *2015 American control conference (ACC)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 5108–5115.
- [11] B. P. Kovatchev, W. L. Clarke, M. Breton, K. Brayman, and A. McCall, “Quantifying temporal glucose variability in diabetes via continuous glucose monitoring: mathematical methods and clinical application,” *Diabetes technology & therapeutics*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 849–862, 2005.
- [12] P. A. Mongini, M. Mazzoleni, A. Ferramosca, L. Magni, and C. Toffanin, “A meal detection approach based on parity space to detect untreated meals in subjects with type 1 diabetes,” in *63rd Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, 2024.